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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boʻlajak oʻqituvchilarda kreativlikni rivojlantirish mavzusi tahlil qilingan boʻlib, ushbu faoliyatning yoʻnalishlari yoritib berilgan. Shuningdek, kreativlik atamasi va turlari, kreativlikni tavsiflaydigan qobiliyatlar, kreativlikning rivojlanish bosqichlari, kreativ faoliyatni tashkil etishga imkon beradigan malakalar guruhlarini, Kreativ mutaxassis xislatlari, kreativlik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishdagi ish shakllari va kreativligining yettita belgisi toʻgʻrisida maʼlumotlar berilgan.

Annotation: This article analyzes the topic of creativity development in future teachers and highlights the directions of this activity. Also, information is provided on the term and types of creativity, abilities that describe creativity, stages of creativity development, groups of skills that allow organizing creative activity, characteristics of a creative specialist, forms of work in the development of creative abilities, and seven signs of creativity.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется тема развития творческих способностей будущих учителей и выделяются направления этой деятельности. Также приведены сведения о термине и видах творчества, способностях, характеризующих творчество, этапах развития творческих способностей, группах умений, позволяющих организовать творческую деятельность, характеристике творческого специалиста, формах работы по развитию творческих способностей и семи признаки творчества.

Kalit soʻzlar: kreativlik, interfaol oʻqitish, novatorlik, kreativ faoliyat, kreativ faollik, kreativ maqsad, nostandart tafakkur

Ключевые слова: творчество, интерактивное обучение, инновации. творческая деятельность, творческая деятельность, творческая цель, нестандартное мышление

Key words: creativity, interactive learning, innovation. tvorcheskaya deyatelnost, tvorcheskaya deyatelnost, tvorcheskaya tsel, nestandartnoe myshlenie

Main part: In our country, as a result of consistent reforms aimed at creating conditions for the development and well-being of a person, the realization of his interests, and bringing the quality and efficiency of education to a new level, opportunities for the development of creative abilities of students are being created on the basis of interactive teaching methods. For example, as stated in the work of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. M. Mirziyoyev,¹ "From

¹ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Milliy tiklanishdan milliy yuksalish sari. J.4.-Toshkent: "Oʻzbekiston", 2020.-456b.

¹ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Yangi Oʻzbekiston strategiyasi.-Toshkent: "Oʻzbekiston", 2021.-464b.

¹ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Xalqimizning roziligi bizning faoliyatimizga berilgan eng oliy bahodir. J.2.-Toshkent: "Oʻzbekiston", 2018.-508b.

¹ M.A Shaxodjaev, L.K.Mamadaliyeva «Kasbiy Faoliyatda Pedagogik Kreativlikning Rivojlantirish Omillari» Monografiya Fargʻona – 2022 169 bet

¹ Talabalarni Ijodiy Yondashuv Asosida Innovatsion Kasbiy Faoliyatga Tayyorlash Imkoniyatlari Toʻxtayeva Zebo Sharifovna 497-503 fayl

national revival to national rise", "Our priority goal is to train specialists who think creatively, have deep knowledge in a specific field of science, and high intellectual potential."

The following comments of our head of state are a confirmation of how important the development of creativity in future teachers is today: on the way, the conceptual foundations of educating modern individuals with an active civic position, creative and innovative thinking have not been developed. This once again proves the existence of a serious gap in the field." It should be noted here that the President's opinion in his work entitled "People's approval is the highest value given to our activities" is the basis for extensive work in this field. serves as: "Today, in order to renew and modernize our country, to develop it on an innovative basis, to implement the multifaceted and complex tasks we have set before ourselves, we are modern and creative thinkers who take responsibility in any situation We are entrusting important tasks in state and society management to patriotic young personnel who are able to take on themselves, are enthusiastic, have high intellectual potential.

In order to fully understand the general essence of the process of developing creative qualities in a person, it is first of all important to understand the meaning of the concept of "creativity".

Creativity (lating, "create" - creation, "creative" - creator) is the creative ability of an individual that describes the readiness to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor.

Creativity - this component refers to the teacher's ability to create and implement new ideas. The development of creativity goes from imitative activity in the creation of projects to real creativity, as a result of which the teacher creates a new method of education and upbringing.

Creativity can be called a desire for creativity, a creative approach to life, a constant critical look at oneself and analysis. Based on the modern dictionaries of psychology and pedagogy, it can be defined as the teacher's creativity, the level of his/her thoughts, feelings, communication, special activity, creative approach, knowledge level.

According to E. P. Torrens, the basis of the concept of "creativity" is explained as follows:

- to put forward a problem or scientific hypothesis;
- checking and changing the hypothesis;
- identifying the problem based on the formation of decision results;
 - sensitivity to the conflict between knowledge and workshop actions in finding a solution to a problem.

J. Guilford shows a number of individual abilities that characterize creativity:

- to be able to direct the thought according to the purpose;
- uniqueness (originality);
- curiosity;
- the ability to create hypotheses;
- to be able to imagine (fantasy).²

^{2 2} Guilford J.P. (1950) Creativity, American Psychologist, Volume 5, Issue 9, 444–454

² . Ибрагимова Г.Н. Интерфаол укитиш методлари ва технологиялари асосида талабаларнинг креативлик қобилиятларини ривожлантириш. / Монография. – Т.: “Фан ва технологиялар”, 2016. – Б. 77

Future teachers should be able to convey ideas to students in an appropriate way during the course of the lesson and during their scientific activities, and in order to reflect their individuality, to regularly enrich scientific activity and their own knowledge, they should have the ability to be curious, create hypotheses and imagine. His ability to get things is a clear example of his creativity.

The development of creativity in today's future teachers is important, and the stages of creativity development are interpreted as follows.

Researcher G. Ibragimova described the stages of creativity development in learners during interactive teaching as follows:

✚ Reproductive risk stage. This stage is characterized by the determination of creative activity, creative activity and inclination to creativity in students, understanding of the essence of innovative technologies in education, and the birth and formation of new ideas.

✚ Creative research stage. It is determined by the formation of research, creative activity, non-standard thinking, cognitive independence, improvisation, and innovation skills in students.

✚ Creativity, innovation stage. It includes processes related to the practical application, evaluation, analysis, popularization and wide implementation of the created innovation, as well as the creation of future-oriented strategic plans. along with hu, it is also required to have the ability to apply the existing innovation through creative approaches.

A teacher's creativity is his ability to find various original ideas in strict, limited or loosely limited conditions. *Analysis of scientific literature allows to distinguish the following interrelated structural components of creativity:*

- ✓ Intellectual (mental).
- ✓ Moral (self-control).
- ✓ Motivational (purposeful).
- ✓ Emotional (emotional).

Creativity consists of the following interrelated parts:

1. Creative purpose.
2. Creative pursuit.
3. Building a creative (installation).
4. Creative direction.
5. Creative expressive act.
6. Creative self-management.
7. Creative activity.
8. Level of creative aspirations.

The teacher's creativity appears and develops in his creative activity. Creativity is seen in the teacher's creative desire, creative ability, creative goal, direction and ability to control himself in his creative activity, and it is a mature developing, growing student with his own activity, self-control. means becoming a person³

³ Developing creative qualities in students Bakhtiyor SIDDIKOV, Erkin Abdullaev Ferghana State University Article Info Abstract Article history: Received September 2021 Received in revised form 15 September 2021 Accepted 20 October 2021 Available online 15 November 2021

It is also necessary to form a number of skills that will enable the development of creativity in pedagogues.

Groups of qualifications that allow teachers to organize creative activities:

- ✓ cognitive (gnostic) qualifications;
- ✓ design skills;
- ✓ creative-seminar (constructive) skills;
- ✓ research skills;
- ✓ accessibility to communication (communicative) skills;
- ✓ organizational skills;
- ✓ consistency (procedural) skills;
- ✓ technical and technological skills

It is important to use the following forms of work in the development of students' creativity:

- organization of trainings that serve to develop the skills of data analysis, quick decision-making, and creative thinking;
- performing creative exercises and assignments aimed at forming imaginations and visual views;
- working with cases;
- organization of group work forms and debates;
- preparation of educational projects;
- formation of portfolios;
- organizing castings;
- establishing activities of clubs, etc

There are the following criteria for determining the level of development of students' creativity:

- *determination of motivation for creative activity;*
- *development of creative thinking skills;*
- *formation of creative qualities;*
- *organizing the process of practical creative activity;*
- *the formation of specialized creativity, etc.*

A teacher-innovator should be a productive creative person, a lover of creativity, wide-ranging interest and occupation, a rich inner world, and be keen on pedagogical innovations.

Professional skills, knowledge, and creativity of the teacher are the main factors in the formation of conscious activity and independence in students. During the period of pedagogical practice, the work of the future pedagogue-educator in the school becomes important in the formation of their professional skills. From this it can be concluded that if the teacher is knowledgeable and creative, it serves as an important factor in the formation of a number of abilities, such as conscious activity and creativity, independence in his students.⁴

⁵***Scientist V.A. Molyako lists seven signs of student creativity:***

⁴ Innovatsion Pedagogika Toshkent Shahar Sergeli Tumani 7-Orta Ta' Lim Maktabining Boshlan'gich Sinf O'qituvchisi Aripova Gavhar Xamitovna

⁵ O'zbekistonda Fanlararo Innovatsiyalar va 10-Son Ilmiy Tadqiqotlar Jurnalida 20.08.2022 112 Bo'lajak O'qituvchilarni Innovatsion Faoliyatga Tayyorlashning Pedagogik Asoslari Qubonzoda Sevara Raxmatali Qizi Farg'ona Davlat Universiteti II Bosqich Magistrant

- ✓ not being like others,
- ✓ heuristics,
- ✓ -fantasy,
- ✓ -activity,
- ✓ focused attention,
- ✓ -independence of thoughts,
- ✓ -accuracy,
- ✓ -sensitivity.

A creative specialist must have the following qualities: ingenuity, self-criticism, critical attitude, flexibility of thinking, courage and bravery, enthusiasm, persistence, determination to finish the work, goal orientation.

A.H. Maslow divides creativity into 2 types:

- creativity of talent
- -personal self-actualization creativity.

Since the creativity of self-actualization of the individual is inextricably linked with the personality, we can encounter it in everyday life and in many areas of professional activity.

A.H. Maslow identified two levels of self-actualization in creativity:

1. the first - "involuntary creativity, in which a person suddenly comes to his senses, is inspired, has difficult experiences",
2. "the second - voluntary, hard work, continuous education, striving for perfection".

A.H. Maslow believes that creativity is a fundamental characteristic of human nature, that is, an innate ability that all people have, but that is lost during life as a result of certain social barriers.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the following should be taken into account in the development of creativity in future teachers:

- ✚ to fundamentally improve the personnel potential of the higher education system, to increase the professional prestige of teachers, teachers and pedagogues;
- ✚ structural restructuring of the continuing education system;
- ✚ development of abilities such as uniqueness, heuristics, fantasy, activity, concentration, independence of thoughts, precision, sensitivity;
- ✚ organization of trainings that serve to develop the skills of data analysis, quick decision-making, and creative thinking;
- ✚ performing creative exercises and tasks aimed at forming imaginations and imaginative views;
- ✚ working with cases during the lesson;
- ✚ organization of group work forms and debates among students;
- ✚ preparation of educational projects;
- ✚ -formation of portfolios;
- ✚ organizing castings;
- ✚ establishing the activities of clubs, etc

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